

Being Transformed in the Image and Glory of God (2 Cor 3:18)

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How can we live a life that expresses God? God's way is to give us His divine life, and for us to undergo an organic change by His life operating in us. God wants us to change, but not the way we might think. In fact, the Bible speaks of transformation according to the Word of God. It is understandable to think that transformation for Christians means we improve ourselves or our behaviour so we appear more "Christ-like." But the biblical meaning of transformation has nothing to do with our outward behaviour or self-improvement, but to transform into the same image and glory of God (2 Cor 3:18). We shall look at what transformation means according to the Word of God.

The Apostle Paul experienced a dramatic story of radical transformation. He was actively persecuting Christians until Jesus met him on the road to Damascus (Acts 9). Paul's life was immediately turned around. From that point forward he advocated for the gospel of Jesus Christ as zealously as he had persecuted Christians in the past. Therefore, he could teach us about spiritual transformation out of his experience of personal transformation.

St. Paul exhorts the Romans that we should not be conformed to this world, but be transformed by the renewing of our mind, so that we may prove what the will of God is, that which is good and acceptable and perfect (Rom 12:2). Paul urges us to resist the pattern of the world. The more we trust God, recognizing his mercy, and the more we surrender to and worship him, the better we will be able to defy worldly attitudes (cf. Rom 12:1-2). As we resist the world, we intentionally renew our minds with God's Word. God gave us his Word, and reading it is the best way to renew our minds. Renewing our minds is a means by which God chooses to perform his transformative work. We can read, study, and apply his Word, but we depend on the Holy Spirit to transform us, as it "comes from the Lord who is the Spirit" (2 Cor 3:18). Paul also urges us to discern what is the will of God

in the process of transformation: “... that by testing you may discern what is the will of God, what is good and acceptable and perfect” (Rom 12:2). When we surrender our lives to God in view of his mercy, worship him with everything we are, resist the pattern of the world, and renew our minds by his Spirit, then we will be able to discern God’s will (cf. Rom 12:1-2). According to Paul, this process that begins with surrendering to discerning God’s will leads to personal transformation. In short, in the Bible transformation means to change or renewal from a life that no longer conforms to the ways of the world to one that pleases God (cf. Rom 12:2). This is accomplished by the renewing of our minds, an inward spiritual transformation that will manifest itself in outward actions (cf. Rom 12:2).

Likewise, St. Paul teaches the Corinthians that we all, with unveiled face, beholding as in a mirror the glory of the Lord, are being transformed into the same image from glory to glory, just as from the Lord, the Spirit. Here, being transformed is connected to our beholding the glory of the Lord. So what are we transformed into? 2 Cor 3:18 tells us we are “being transformed into the same image” of God. That is, the transformation within us is seen in the way we increasingly reflect the likeness and glory of Christ (2 Cor 3:18). This is exactly what God wants, for us to be “conformed to the image of his Son” (Rom 8:29). Further, St Paul teaches us that by God’s power we can transform our humble state of the body into conformity with the body of His glory (Phil 3:21), and we will all be changed by the power of his resurrection (cf. 1Cor 15:21). In short, when we with unveiled face reflect the glory of the Lord, the Lord infuses us with his power and nature. When we behold the Lord in our fellowship with Him, something wonderful happens. Thus we are being transformed metabolically to have His life and His essence; that is, we are being transfigured, mainly by the renewing of our mind (Rom. 12:2), into His image. For anyone who is in Christ is a new creation (2 Cor 5:17). Paul further teaches that this transformed life in Christ is demonstrated through our “bearing fruit in every good work [and] growing in the knowledge of God” (Col 1:10).

The transformed life mirrors the attitude of Paul: “I have been crucified with Christ and I no longer live, but Christ lives in me. The life I live in the body, I live by faith in the Son of God, who loved me and gave himself for me” (Gal 2:20). When Christ dwells in us, He is incarnated in our lives – in our thoughts, attitudes, actions, words, and relationships. We make Jesus visible in our lives through the way we live and serve; people see Him when they interact with us: Indeed, there is a strong connection between Christ-likeness and mission: Christ-likeness leads to mission, and mission is meaningless without Christ-likeness. When we are transformed into Christ’s likeness, it is no longer we who live, but Christ who lives in us (Gal 2:20). So, our will becomes His will, and our minds

think His thoughts. When Christ lives in us, we will learn to do what he wants, we will reflect his character in all our actions and relationships, and we will fulfill his mission by extending His ministry and Kingdom through our lives. In short, He becomes visible in our lives.

St. Paul further argues that transformed life begins with the gospel message of Christ, for it is the power of God in the gospel that brings us salvation: “I am not ashamed of the gospel, because it is the power of God for the salvation of everyone who believes: first for the Jew, then for the Gentile. For in the gospel a righteousness from God is revealed, a righteousness that is by faith from first to last, just as it is written: ‘The righteous will live by faith’” (Rom 1:16-17). Therefore, Paul says that through the gospel message of Christ, we learn to put off our old self, which belongs to our former manner of life and is corrupt through deceitful desires, and to be renewed in the spirit of our minds, and to put on the new self, created after the likeness of God in true righteousness and holiness (Eph 4:22-24).

Transformation involves those who were once far from God being “drawn near” to Him through the blood of Christ (Eph 2:13). For Paul says, “if you live according to the sinful nature, you will die; but if by the Spirit you put to death the misdeeds of the body, you will live, because those who are led by the Spirit of God are sons of God” (Rom 8:13-14).

Being transformed indicates that we are in the process of transformation. As we undergo this process, we are not merely becoming a better person, but we gradually change to match the Lord. This is because bit by bit, we are being conformed to His image and being made the same as He is. Prophet Ezekiel says “I will give you a new heart, and a new spirit I will put within you. And I will remove the heart of stone from your flesh and give you a heart of flesh” (Ezek 36:26). Transformation will give us a new heart, and a new spirit for the mission and our living together in community. And as St Paul says he who began a good work in us will bring it to completion at the day of Jesus Christ (Phil 1:6).